

and 5 pairs of moths released. After 3 d, the number of eggs laid on leaves of different widths did not differ.

CW reared on potted 2- to 6-wk-old rice had shorter larval development period and higher larval weight, and growth index, survivorship, and fertility (Table 2).

We conclude that suitable oviposition sites occur only during the vegetative stage. CW on older rice have low survival and slow development. □

Table 2. Effect of rice plant age on growth and development of *N. depunctalis*.^a IRRI greenhouse, 1983-84.

Plant age ^b (WT)	Larval wt (mg)	Larval developmental period (d)	Growth index ^c	Survivorship from larva to adulthood (d)	Fertility (no. of eggs/female)
2	5.76 b	18 ab	4.7 ab	65 a	111 a
4	7.07 a	15 a	5.6 a	69 a	117 a
6	8.24 a	17 a	4.3 b	63 a	108 a
8	4.47 c	21 c	2.7 c	37 b	67 b
10	3.89 d	20 bc	2.1 c	36 b	74 b

^a Av of 6 replications of 25 insects each replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. ^b Transplanted 3 wk after germination.

^c Growth index = pupation (%) / larval developmental period (d).

Bioefficacy of seven insecticides against leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée in India

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A replicated trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design in 1984 kharif at the HPAU Rice Research Station to evaluate seven insecticides: quinalphos, carbofuran, monocrotophos, benfuracarb, bromophos-ethyl, ethoprop, and UC54229. Insecticides were applied as needed at 26 and 38 d after transplanting (DT). Damage was

assessed at 50 DT.

All insecticides were superior to the untreated control (see table).

UC54229, quinalphos, and monocrotophos are promising for checking leaffolder damage. □

Effect of 7 insecticides on leaffolder damage and yield of cultivar Himalaya 1 at Malan, H. P., India, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Leaffolder damage (%)	Damage decrease (%)	Grain yield (t/ha) ^a	Yield increase (%)
Quinalphos 3G	1.5	1.5 d	89.3	3.9 a	61.6
Carbofuran 3G	1.0	2.3 cd	83.6	3.4 b	40.6
Monocrotophos 40EC	0.5	1.9 cd	86.5	3.1 bc	29.0
Benfuracarb 3G	1.5	2.7 c	80.8	3.0 cd	25.5
Bromophos-ethyl 5G	1.5	2.4 c	82.9	2.9 cd	23.2
Ethoprop 10G	1.5	3.7 b	73.7	2.7 de	13.9
UC 54229 99SP	0.75	1.3 d	90.7	2.7 de	11.6
Untreated control	—	14.1 a	—	2.4 e	—

^a In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

Nuclear polyhedrosis virus for controlling the ear-cutting caterpillar

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The ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Walker) damages rice in the Solomon Islands. The mature caterpillar cuts the panicles of ripening rice. Early infestations are minor but a late infestation with old larvae causes serious damage and heavy yield loss. The immature stage consists of six larval stadia; larvae of the last two instars are ravenous feeders. In the field, a viral disease occasionally caused high mortality of young larvae.

M. separata's nuclear polyhedrosis virus (*Ms* NPV) was first studied in the

early 1970s in India, but the virus has not been formulated and used commercially. *Authographa californica*'s NPV (*A.cal* NPV) was first isolated in the early 1960s from a diseased larva in a California alfalfa field. *A.cal* NPV has a large host spectrum including 9 families (Lepidoptera), 29 genera, and 35 species of insect pests. This has aroused worldwide interest in its potential as a broad-spectrum microbial control agent.

We used *Ms*NPV and *A.cal* NPV from the Institute of Virology (IOV), Oxford, U.K., to test insects collected from the Solomons. The bioassay was conducted at the IOV in Oct 1985.

Larvae of *M. separata* were reared on an artificial diet with basic elements

from brewer yeast and red kidney bean extracts. Thirty 2d-instar larvae were used for each of three replications per treatment. With a vacuum suction device, 10 mg of the diet was put in a compartment of a transparent multicompartment plate. One larva was placed in each of the other compartments. Then the viral suspension was released onto the diet at 1 µl/larva. Untreated control insects were fed with the same diet and water. At 3 d after treatment (DAT), all insects were transferred into 4-cm-diam butter cups filled to 1.5 cm depth with the diet, at 1 larva/cup.

Mortality was recorded at 7 and 14 DAT. The midgut of dead larvae was smeared on slides and stained with naphthalene black for diagnosis under

a microscope (1000X). Mortality of larvae in the untreated control was 0.3% at 7 DAT and 0.7% at 14 DAT. Mortality of the treated insects was adjusted using Abbott's formula (see table).

The results indicate that *A.cal* NPV is pathogenic to *M. separata*. Differences in insect mortality were greater at 14 DAT. Treated insects that died without being affected by the virus were those that failed to eat during the first few days.

Effects of the viruses in the field would depend on application method and formulation to give proper distribution-deposition and protection from ultraviolet and other adverse factors. The virus is projected to be

Mortality of *Mythimna separata* (Walk.) treated with nuclear polyhedrosis virus.^a

Treatment		Mortality ^c (%)	
Virus	Dosage ^b (PIB/ml)	7 DAT	14 DAT
<i>A. cal</i> NPV	6.675×10^4	3.2 b	6.7 d
	6.675×10^5	10.0 ab	23.3 c
	6.675×10^6	16.3 ab	31.7 bc
	6.675×10^7	15.7 ab	36.7 b
	6.675×10^8	34.7 a	83.3 a
<i>Ms</i> NPV	3.540×10^4	3.0 c	3.3 d
	3.540×10^5	23.7 b	36.7 b
	3.540×10^6	35.7 b	53.3 ab
	3.540×10^7	41.0 ab	83.3 a
	3.540×10^8	62.0 a	96.7 a

^aThirty 2d-instar larvae replication, 3 replications/treatment. ^bPIB = polyhedral inclusion bodies. ^cMeans in a column followed by common letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

used at Solrice farm next year, together with the parasite *Apanteles ruficrus* Haliday (Braconidae -

Hymenoptera), to control *M. separata*. □

Rice leafroller (LF) complex in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

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During 1985–86 rabi (winter Nov planting), recommended chemicals did not give adequate control of LF in the Madurai Agricultural College Farm. The larvae were collected periodically and reared to adults.

We found that LF is a complex of three species: *Cnaphalocrocis*

Survey of rice LF in Madurai, India, 1985.

Date collected	LF adults that emerged (no.)		
	<i>C. medinalis</i>	<i>M. patnalis</i>	<i>M. ruralis</i>
26 Sep	107	115	1
27 Sep	25	17	–
28 Sep	43	46	–
29 Sep	30	30	1
30 Sep	13	3	–
1 Oct	29	25	1
2 Oct	45	38	–
10 Oct	4	16	–
14 Oct	2	7	–
Total	298	297	3

medinalis, *Marasmia patnalis*, and *Marasmia ruralis*. The first two were abundant on all sampling dates (see

table). Insecticides need to be screened against all three LF species. □

Effect of 3 granular insecticides on brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) in the Easternghat Highland Zone, Koraput, India

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In the Easternghat Highland Zone, Koraput district, India, serious BPH outbreaks were observed on irrigated

Effect of granular insecticides on BPH population and rice yield at Semiliguda, Koraput, India, 1981.^a

Insecticide	Adults/hill (treatment at 15 DT)		Nymphs/hill (treatment at 35 DT)		Yield (t/ha)
	10 DAT	20 DAT	10 DAT	20 DAT	
Untreated	13.7 d	59.0 e	27.0 d	0.0	0.0
BPMC	4.7 a	51.7 de	7.3 b	27.7 b	1.5 a
Carbofuran	5.7 ab	35.7 a	6.3 b	34.7 b	1.8 a
Isoprocarb	7.0 bc	42.3 abc	4.3 a	21.0 a	1.7 a
Phorate	8.0 bc	43.3 bc	19.0 cd	0.0	0.0
Disulfoton	8.7 c	41.3 ab	13.0 c	0.0	0.0
Quinalphos	9.3 c	49.3 cd	18.3 cd	0.0	0.0

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level after logarithmic transformation. DT = days after transplanting.